

HOLOCENE VEGETATION IN NORTHWESTERN ARABIA - CHANGING NATURAL RESOURCES.

Michèle Dinies^{1,2}, Reinder Neef¹, Birgit Plessen³, Harald Kürschner²

¹Scientific Department of the Head Office, German Archaeological Institute (DAI), Im Dol 2-6,
14195 Berlin, Germany

²Institute of Biology, Freie Universität Berlin, Altensteinstraße 6, 14195 Berlin, Germany

³Section 5.2, Climate Dynamics and Landscape Evolution, German Research Centre for Geosciences
(GFZ), Telegrafenberg, 14473 Potsdam, Germany

michele.dinies@fu-berlin.de

rn@dainst.de

birgit.plessen@gfz-potsdam.de

kuersch@zedat.fu-berlin.de

Résumé : La végétation est l'une des ressources naturelles les plus importantes pour les humains et les animaux (sauvages et domestiques). Des changements de la végétation au cours de l'Holocène sont documentés par un diagramme pollinique provenant de Tayma, dans le Nord-Ouest de l'Arabie Saoudite. Les résultats palynologiques suggèrent une courte "période humide au début de l'Holocène", suivie par des conditions arides pendant près de 2000 ans. Vers 6300 cal BP, période à laquelle la culture d'arbres fruitiers est documentée dans l'oasis de Tayma, des conditions légèrement humides peuvent avoir dominées. Bien que depuis au moins (la fin) du milieu de l'Holocène l'activité humaine est enregistrée, la variabilité climatique semble être d'une importance majeure pour les changements de végétation - et donc pour les changements des ressources naturelles dans la région Tayma.

Abstract : Vegetation is one of the most important natural resources for humans and animals (wild and domestic). Holocene vegetation shifts are documented in a pollen diagram of Tayma in northwestern Saudi Arabia. The palynological results suggest a short "early Holocene humid period", followed by arid conditions for nearly 2000 years. Around 6300 cal BP, contemporaneous with the beginning of fruit tree cultivation at the oasis of Tayma, slightly wetter conditions may have prevailed. Although at least since (the end) of the mid-Holocene human impact is recorded, climate seems to be the major driver for the Holocene vegetation shifts – and thus for the changes of the natural, biotic resources in the Tayma region.

Mots-clés : Palynologie, oasis de Tayma, Arabie Saoudite, ressources biotiques, climat Holocène.

Keywords : Pollen analysis, oasis Tayma, Saudi Arabia, biotic resources, Holocene climate.

Ecosystems of (semi)-desert regions like northwestern Arabia are sensitive to both, climatic changes and human impact. Vegetation changes in northwestern Arabia may have been triggered by climate during the Holocene, as recorded in e.g. sediments of the northern part of the Red Sea, the eastern Mediterranean Sea, the Dead Sea, speleothems or other palaeoenvironmental proxies (e.g. Arz *et al.*, 2003; Bar-Matthews *et al.*, 1999; Develle *et al.*, 2010; Migowski *et al.*, 2006; Roberts *et al.*, 2011; Rossignol-Strick, 1999; Verheyden *et al.*, 2008). Human populations may as well have changed the vegetation, as stated for the adjacent southern part of the Mediterranean floristic region, e.g. Jordan, Israel. The natural vegetation was not only suppressed by the invention/introduction of agriculture but by "[...] the abuse of vegetation [...] Also in the deserts, the enormous cover of the present vegetation is far from being original or primary. It has been very strongly effected by man who since his very advent has not stopped collecting, burning, cutting and grazing" (Zohary, 1982). Thus, at least since the neolithisation process, when human populations started crop plant cultivation and animal husbandry, climate and/or land use are drivers of vegetation shifts in the Near East and adjacent regions (e.g. Woldring, 2002; Köhler-Rollefson, 1988).

Concurrently vegetation is the main natural biotic resource of a region : The dominating vegetation is a major component of the biome which in turn indicates the range of possible subsistence strategies such as foraging, herding or agricultural practices (e.g. Cramer, 2002). By means of continuous pollen diagrams the vegetation of a region can be reconstructed for past periods, and thus a main natural, biotic resource. As mentioned, climate and human impact are the two primary drivers of vegetation changes during the Holocene. Yet, by correlating and synchronizing the vegetation shifts with other palaeoenvironmental proxies the driver(s) may be defined.

Bordering at the Levant, northwestern Saudi Arabia is a region in which archaeologists became increasingly interested during the last decades. Ongoing archaeological research considers small scaled human impact during early Holocene (Fujii, 2006). Since about 6000 cal BP water management seems to be established (Brückner *et al.*, 2002; Gebel, 2013) and since the Late Bronze Age there is evidence for large oasis settlements with elaborated agriculture (e.g. Hausleiter *et al.*, 2014; Luciani, 2014).

Up to now, continuous Holocene palynological records for northwestern Arabia are missing. Holocene vegetation shifts and hence changing natural biotic resources could only be hypothesized. The so far oldest evidence for crop plant cultivation in northwestern Saudi Arabia – archaeobotanical samples out of archaeological context of the oasis settlement of Tayma – dates to the second half of the 3rd millennium BCE (various cereals, beets, lentils, grapes, figs, pomegranates and *Prunus* sp., Neef, unpublished data). The ongoing archaeological investigations suggest the beginnings of the Tayma oasis settlements around the 1st half of the 2nd millenium BCE (e.g. Eichmann, 2011; Hausleiter *et al.*, 2014).

Based on results of the ongoing palynological investigations at Tayma¹, the early and mid-

¹Since 2004 the Saudi-German Joint Archaeological Project at the oasis of Tayma is excavating the old oasis settlements. From the start, palaeoenvironmental and geoarchaeological investigations were involved in this archaeological project. The sabkha north of the oasis town of Tayma (a lake during the early and mid-Holocene) proved to be an excellent palaeoenvironmental archive. Therefore, additional projects were initiated to investigate different proxies at the sediments of the palaeolake of Tayma (actual vegetation and palynology : Kürschner, Neef and Dinies, see Kürschner and Neef, 2011; Dinies *et al.*, 2015; microfauna, diatoms, geo/biochemistry and sedimentology : Engel, Frenzel, Gleixner, Hoelzmann, Neugebauer, Pint, Plessen, Schwarz; see Engel *et al.*, 2012).

Holocene vegetation changes, their (probable) drivers and their implications for human populations will be synthesized. The palynologically recorded beginning of fruit tree cultivation at the oasis of Tayma, preceding the up to now oldest crop cultivation records, is the oldest unambiguous indicator for human impact (primary anthropogenic indicator, c.f. Behre, 1981, 1990). The analysis of our results will also help to answer the question, whether human land use was relevant or not for shaping the natural vegetation during the 1st half of the Holocene in the Tayma region.

Study Site

The oasis of Tayma is situated in the northwest of Saudi Arabia (27°38' N, 38°33' E, ca 830 asl). In the west, about 100 km from Tayma, the Hijaz Mountains run from the north to the south. In the east, the western fringes of the sand desert Nafud borders the Tayma region. Paleozoic rocks ('Nubian'/Cambrian sandstones) dominate, along with some cenozoic volcanic rocks (www.sgs.org.sa). For the position of the investigated cores Tay 220 out of the sabkha north of Tayma and an overview over the study site see Figure 1 and Figure 2.

FIG. 1. Location of the study region Tayma and the palaeolake near Tayma, the coring site Tay 220 and – in white - the coring transect through the sabkha of Engel *et al.*, 2012.

The Tayma region is part of the arid interior of Saudi Arabia. Mean annual rainfall of Tabuk - the nearest meteorological station - is 29.3 mm. There are extreme inter-annual fluctuations of rainfall amounts. The mean annual temperature is about 19° C (Almazroui *et al.*, 2012; meteoblue).

Four main desert vegetation types dominate at present the Tayma region. Typical for the vast rock (hammada) and gravel deserts (reg) is a vegetation dominated by various *Fagonia* species which is replaced on the extended sandy desert plains by two desert shrubland types : The “rimth” shrubland with *Haloxylon salicornicum* (Chenopodiaceae), mixed with the “arfaj” shrubland, dominated

FIG. 2. Panoramic view with the excavation area in the foreground and the sabkha and the sandstone escarpment in the background, in between the 'old town' and palm groves.

by *Rhanterium epapposum* (Asteraceae). Both are most common in north Saudi-Arabia. On the sand dunes the “adhir” shrubland dominates, formed by *Artemisia jordanica* and *Calligonum comosum*. A chorotype analysis of these plant communities documents the strong Saharo-Arabian character and origin of the recent vegetation in the Tayma area (Kürschner and Neef, 2011 ; Pandalayil, 2015).

Material and Methods

RADIOMETRIC DATING AND AGE DEPTH MODEL

The preliminary radiometric chronology is based on ^{14}C dated pollen concentrations. Different protocols were combined to extract pollen for dating (mainly Brown *et al.*, 1989 ; Brown *et al.*, 1992 ; Regnéll and Everitt, 1996 ; Nakagawa *et al.*, 1998). Because of the low pollen concentration of the sediment, up to 15 cm (3-15 cm) had to be processed. The pollen were extracted from two nearby cores (< 2m), Tay 220 and Tay 254.

The samples were dated by accelerator mass spectrometry (AMS) ^{14}C dating at the Poznan Radiocarbon Laboratory.

The ^{14}C dates were calibrated using BCal (BCal 2014 ; Buck *et al.*, 1999). The dates incorporated in the age depth model were calibrated together, considering their stratigraphic position. The open source program psimpoll was used to calculate the linear age depth model (Bennett, 1997-2007).

FIG. 3. Diagram showing selected pollen types (percentages calculated against the sum of terrestrial pollen types) and TOC. The suffix type indicates that this pollen type includes more taxa than the mentioned genus. On the left a simplified stratigraphy. Data are plotted versus years cal BP.

POLLEN ANALYSIS

About 5-10 cm³ of Tay 220 has been sampled in varying intervals, between 15-2 cm. The samples were prepared using standard techniques (Faegri and Iversen, 1989; Moore *et al.*, 1999; Eisele *et al.*, 1994). Marker spores were added, allowing to calculate pollen concentrations (Stockmarr, 1971).

Pollen have been determined using atlases of pollen morphology (e.g. Beug, 2004; Bonnefille and Riollet, 1980; El Ghazali, 1991; Reille, 1992), the reference slide collection of the DAI Berlin and the pollen images of the African Pollen Database.

The palynological results of the ongoing investigations are summarized in a percentage pollen diagram showing only selected types (Figure 3). The zonation of the percentage pollen diagram follows changes in the frequencies of dominating types.

GEOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS : TOC CONTENT

For elemental analysis about 1 cm³ every 2-3 cm has been sampled from Tay 220, freeze dried and powdered down to <63 µm. Total organic carbon (TOC) was determined using an elemental analyzer (NC2500 Carlo Erba). The TOC contents were determined on in-situ decalcified samples. Around 3 mg of sample material was weighted into Ag-capsules, dropped with 20% HCl, heated for 3h at 75°C, and finally wrapped and measured as described above. The calibration was performed using elemental standards (Acetanilide, Urea) and proofed with an internal soil reference sample (Boden3). The reproducibility for replicate analyzes is 0.2%.

Results

LITHOLOGY

In Table 1 the main sedimentological changes are summarized.

Depth below surface	
0-100 cm	rust-red silty sand; no pollen preserved
100-163 cm	grey marl, rich in small gypsum crystals, alternating with rust-red and grey loamy thin layers; no pollen preserved
163-326 cm	grey marl, rich in small gypsum crystals, with lighter and darker grey, mainly loamy thin layers and, especially in the basal part, large (posthum) gypsum crystals; down 163 cm pollen are preserved
326-384 cm	brownish-grey marl, rich in small gypsum crystals, coarsely laminated by alternating darker and lighter grey and brownish layers, partially richer in crystals, partially more loamy
384-415 cm	transition to brownish-grey marl, coarsely laminated, to dark brownish-grey finely laminated sediments
415-508 cm	dark brownish-grey, finely laminated marl with whitish, grey and brownish laminae; in the upper part with small crystals, mainly confined to thin, distinct laminae
508-600 cm	grey marl, with whitish and lighter and darker grey layers (loamy and/or sand/shell fragments), with (large) gypsum crystals and basal with large concretions
> 600 cm	bedrock

TAB. 1. Strongly simplified stratigraphy of Tay 220, summarizing the main sedimentological changes.

DATING RESULTS AND AGE DEPTH MODEL

The dating results are summarized in Table 2. Dating results incorporated in the age depth model were calibrated by considering their stratigraphic position. Omitted dates are commented. The preliminary linear age depth model is shown in Figure 4.

FIG. 4. A linear age depth model of Tay 220, based on radiometric determinations of pollen concentrations with $\geq 50\%$ pollen, using the open source program psimpoll (Bennett, 1997-2007).

PALYNOLOGY

Selected pollen types and the TOC values are plotted against the age in cal years BP, showing the major changes during the early to late Holocene (see Figure 3). The characteristic features and main changes of the different zones are summarized in Table 3.

Discussion

THE TAYMA POLLEN DIAGRAM – A REGIONAL POLLEN RECORD

The interpretation of the Tayma pollen diagram is based on the assumption that the record mainly documents the regional vegetation dynamics. Several clues support this assumption :

- The sedimentation basin is large. The sabkha, during the early and mid-Holocene a lake, covers an

	Depth cm	material dated	mg C	Lab Code	¹⁴ C bp	cal BP (2 σ)	reasons why omitted/ contamination by
AMS_20	167-180	75% pollen; 10-15% charred particles; <5% tissues	0.5	Poz-62344	4345 ± 35	4980-4670	
AMS_21	180-198	80% pollen; 15% charred particles; 5% tissues	n.s.	Poz-62562	4360 ± 40	4840-5030	
AMS_22	198-209	85% pollen; 10-15% charred particles; 5% tissues	0.5	Poz-62345	4200 ± 40	4845-5205	
AMS_3	202-208	60% pollen; 30% tissues; 5% charred particles; 5% limnic NPP	n.s.	Poz-55862*	5010 ± 50*		2 small samples merged contamination?
AMS_23	226-237	80% pollen; 10% charred particles; 10% tissues	0.5	Poz-62553	4780 ± 50	5295-5655	
AMS_24	237-248	80% pollen; 10% charred particles; 10% tissues	0.3	Poz-62554	4840 ± 70	5350-5905	
AMS_4ws		root/stem fragment	0.1	Poz-55866*	4360 ± 100		very small amount of C
AMS_30	272-280	70% pollen; 25% tissues; 5% charred particles	n.s.	Poz-62556	5240 ± 35	5890-6180	
AMS_31	272-280	70% pollen; 30% tissues; small amounts of NPP & charred particles	n.s.	Poz-62347*	5660 ± 30*		?
AMS_32	308-313	95% pollen; 5% tissues	0.6	Poz-62557	5430 ± 40	6285-6000	
AMS_33	315-328	80% pollen; 10% tissues; 10% charred particles	n.s.	Poz-62559	5435 ± 35	6115-6310 (pooled mean)	
AMS_33 charcoal	315-328	90% charred particles; 10% tissues and pollen	n.s.	Poz-62558	5420 ± 40		
AMS_5a	327-331	80% pollen; 10% charred particles; 10% tissues	0.18	Poz-54258	5440 ± 100	6710-6180	
AMS_34	342-350	85% pollen; 10% tissues; 5% charred particles	0.5	Poz-62560	6000 ± 50	6185-6715	
AMS_6	364-369	80% pollen; 15% tissues; 5% charred particles	0.4	Poz-55863	6880 ± 40	7580-7900	
AMS_7	378-382	50% pollen; 45% tissues; 5% charred partilces	0.4	Poz-55864	7080 ± 50	7730-8160	
AMS_26	405-418	70% pollen; 25% tissues; 5% charred particles	0.8	Poz-62561	6950 ± 50	7710-7995	
AMS_8a	416-420	50% pollen; 40% limnic NPP; 5% tissues; 5% charred particles	0.4	Poz-54259	7100 ± 50	7790-8170	
AMS_40	458-459	Gastropod shell	0.3	Poz-62348*	8910 ± 70*		hard water effect
AMS_19	496-499	50% pollen; 15% limnic NPP; 20% tissues; 15% charred particles	n.s.	Poz-55868	7590 ± 40	8190-8530	
AMS_14 poll	517-522	80% pollen; 5% tissues; 15% charred particles	0.5	Poz-55869	7660 ± 40	8355-8580	
AMS_14 char	517-527	60% charred particles; 40% pollen	0.2	Poz-55870*	7390 ± 60*		charred particles (?)
AMS_35	523-534	80% pollen; 10% tissues; 10% charred particles; <5% limnic NPP	0.4	Poz-62563	7670 ± 70	8385-8795	
AMS_36	538-552	50% pollen; 35%limnic NPP; 10% tissues; 5% charred particles	0.5	Poz-62564	7940 ± 60	8605-9255	
AMS_36 HK	538-552	90% charred particles; 10% tissues and pollen	0.3	Poz-62566*	8330 ± 80		charred particles (redemption)
AMS_16.1 npp	547-551	75% limnic NPP; 25% pollen	0.2	Poz-55871*	8440 ± 80		hard water effect of limnic NPP ?
AMS_16.1 ruppia	547-551	6 <i>Ruppia</i> seeds (not charred)	0.7	Poz-55872*	8280 ± 50		hard water effect (water plant)
AMS_16.2	547-551	80% pollen; 15% limnic NPP; 5% tissues	0.2	Poz-55874	7880 ± 70	8460-8990	
AMS_17	565-573	35% pollen; 35% tissues; 25% charred particles; 5% limnic NPP	0.3	Poz-55875*	7410 ± 60		charred particles and tissues (?)

TAB. 2. Radiocarbon age determinations of pollen concentrations, charred fragments, *Ruppia* seeds and a gastropod shell out of Tay 220 and the nearby Tay 254 (< 2m). Dates excluded of the age-depth model are marked by asterisks.

Zone	age cal BP	Terrestrial vegetation	lake shore and water vegetation	TOC	sedimentation rates
4	6250-4800	begin of continuous crop record; increasing <i>Capparis</i> frequencies	high <i>Sparganium</i> type frequencies at the end of this zone	very low values	medium to high
4a	6250-5900	slightly increased <i>Artemisia</i> , Poaceae >40µm, <i>Quercus</i> and <i>Pistacia</i> frequencies		slightly increased values, fluctuating	increasing
3	8000-6250	distinct decrease of Poaceae frequencies about 8000 cal BP, increasing <i>Artemisia</i> , <i>Echinophora</i> and <i>Haloxylon</i> -type frequencies; <i>Olea</i> frequencies increase about 7500 cal BP	very low <i>Sparganium</i> type frequencies	low values, only minor fluctuations	very low
2	8700-8000	highest Poaceae frequencies, a short <i>Ephedra</i> -peak at the beginning; further trees are recorded (nearly) continuously and with higher frequencies	higher <i>Sparganium</i> type frequencies during the 1 st half of the zone	highest values, fluctuating	very high
1	9300-8700	at the beginning very high Chenopodiaceae frequencies, subsequently increasing Poaceae and <i>Ephedra</i> frequencies; <i>Celtis</i> is recorded regularly, <i>Quercus</i> , <i>Pistacia</i> , Combretaceae and <i>Acacia</i> and <i>Salix/Tamarix</i> sporadically	fluctuating, partially very high frequencies of <i>Ruppia</i> (pollen and seeds)	rather low at the beginning, then increasing, fluctuating	medium

TAB. 3. The main characteristics of the 4 current pollen zones, divided visually according to fluctuations of the dominating and ecologically and/or economically important pollen types, are summarized.

area of about 20 km² (Engel *et al.*, 2012). The pollen spectra of sediments of large lakes (> 5 ha) are supposed to record the regional vegetation (e.g. Jacobson and Bradshaw, 1981).

- The fluctuations between the successive pollen spectra are unincisive and wind-pollinated types dominate in the Tayma pollen diagram. The few Holocene pollen spectra out of diatomites of the Nafud (Schulz and Whitney, 1986) in contrast show distinct fluctuations between successive pollen spectra. In addition, pollen types of probably local stands such as e.g. *Moltkiopsis* and *Convolvulus*, mainly insect-pollinated underrepresented pollen types co-dominate the pollen spectra. Thus, the pollen spectra of the Nafud seem to represent mainly the local (to extralocal, up to several 100 m around the sedimentation basin, cf. Jacobson and Bradshaw, 1981) vegetation. Yet, the uppermost pollen spectra of the Tayma record may also be (co-)dominated by the local to extralocal vegetation : In this uppermost section the increasingly lumped pollen may indicate a now locally restricted pollen source area, probably due to the now contracted lake surface. Lake contraction is corroborated by high frequencies of *Sparganium* type, a pollen type comprising riverine taxa like different *Sparganium* species and *Typha domingensis*.
- Distinct sand layers are missing and the sand proportions in the sediment are small. Fluvial eroded and transported pollen often is corroded. Based on the continuous good pollen preservation in the Tayma pollen diagram and the minor sand component a minor fluvial input is assumed.

VEGETATION DYNAMICS IN RELATION TO CLIMATE CHANGE

The Chenopodiaceae, representing the desert vegetation (e.g. Davies and Fall, 2001; Lézine *et al.*, 1998; El-Moslimany, 1990), dominate with about 40–70% throughout the sequence. On edaphically unfavourable sites such as gravel sheets without sand layers the vast reg formations (desert vegetation) prevailed and was not affected by increased humidity during the early Holocene.

For sites with increased plant-available water such as slight depressions, in and along wadis, runnels or beneath rock outcrops, sites benefiting from the redistribution/concentration of rainfall (c.f. Cappars 2006, p. 21 following) and the Hijaz mountains in the west, the pollen diagram of Tayma shows a different vegetation cover during the early (and mid) Holocene.

9300–8700 cal BP : Desert vegetation prevailed during the initial lake phase.

The high *Ruppia* frequencies during the first centuries indicate a shallow and brackish water body during the initial lake phase and arid conditions prevailed during the first 500 years as indicated by the strong dominance of desert vegetation.

8700–8000 cal BP : *Ephedra* and grasslands expansion indicating a short early Holocene humid period.

During these seven centuries the grass frequencies (Poaceae) peak. In (semi)arid regions, expanding grasslands indicate increased moisture (e.g. El Moslimany, 1990). Together with highest TOC values, which may reflect a denser vegetation cover as well as a high lake-internal bio-production during this period, this indicates the relative wettest conditions during the Holocene (Dinies *et al.*, 2015).

8000–6300 cal BP : Grasslands retreated abruptly, goosefoots and sagebush expanded, indicating arid conditions.

Around 8000 cal BP the Poaceae frequencies decrease abruptly, while goosefoot taxa (*Haloxylon* type) and sage brush (*Artemisia*) frequencies increase. This vegetation shift – the increase of drought-resistant dwarf-shrublands (*Haloxylon* type) and the decline of grasslands – goes along with other significant changes : The TOC values decline distinctly, probably reflecting diminished plant debris input due to more scattered vegetation cover and a strongly reduced lake-internal bioproduction. Simultaneously sedimentation changed : The lamination of the limnic sediments ends, suggesting a change of the lake system e.g. due to a lake level lowering, and sedimentation rates diminish strongly (Figure 4). These sedimentological changes corroborate the interpretation that the vegetation shift mirror the onset of more arid conditions.

VEGETATION DYNAMICS TRIGGERED BY CLIMATE AND/OR HUMAN IMPACT

6300–5900 cal BP : A sage brush-peak and the onset of high sedimentation rates – a hint to slightly wetter conditions?

Between about 6300 and 5900 cal BP slightly increased sagebush (*Artemisia*) frequencies may indicate slightly wetter conditions. The re-occurrence or slightly increased frequencies of woody taxa in the Tayma pollen diagram (Combretaceae and *Lannea* type, taxa today distributed in southern Arabia, and *Pistacia*, *Celtis* and *Quercus*) seem to corroborate the interpretation of slightly wetter conditions. Yet, human impact can not be ruled out. The beginning of the continuous record of fruit tree cultivation

(summarized in the "crops" curve in Figure 3), and increased sedimentation rates but still low TOC values pointing to erosion, might indicate human impact.

Other (supra)regional palynological and archaeobotanical records suggest slightly wetter conditions too : In the En Gedi pollen diagram about 500 km in the north higher amounts of deciduous oaks and decreased composite frequencies indicate "an increased precipitation to evaporation ratio" about 6300 cal BP (Litt *et al.*, 2012). More frequently recorded juniper seeds and charcoals in archaeological records in southern Jordan (wadi Araba and wadi al-Yutum) around 6300 cal BP were interpreted as lowering of the *Juniperus phoenicea* vegetation belt, indicating slightly wetter conditions, too (Baierle *et al.*, 1989; Neef, 2009). The minor fluctuation in the regional vegetation (slightly increased tree and sage bush frequencies) documented in the Tayma pollen diagram thus may mirror congruently slightly wetter conditions, while the simultaneous higher sedimentation rates may indicate erosion due to locally intensified land use, documented by the beginning of fruit tree cultivation.

6300–4800 cal BP : Crop/Fruit tree cultivation.

At least since about 6300 cal BP local crop cultivation (grapes, flax and probably figs) can be traced at the oasis of Tayma.

HOLOCENE VEGETATION SHIFTS – CHANGING RESOURCES

Vegetation shifts denote natural changing biotic resources. The so far apparent vegetation shifts in the Tayma pollen diagram and their implications are presented in what follows.

Timber and fuel : woody taxa and their possible habitats

In the Tayma pollen diagram several pollen types of woody taxa are recorded. Pollen types include several of even many different plant species. For the following interpretation, the most probable woody species included in the respective pollen type is discussed. The respective pollen type is indicated in brackets, e.g. sumach - woody species (*Rhus* - pollen type). Their habitats are supposed to be the natural oasis, benefiting from the high groundwater table, edaphically favoured sites such as wadis, depressions and runnels where rainfall concentrates and the Hijaz mountains and its foreland in the west.

Local elements :

Tamarix (*Tamarix/Salix*), acacia (*Acacia*) and sumac (*Rhus*) are supposed to have grown in the vicinity of the palaeolake of Tayma. Until today tamarix and acacia build local stands and sumac occurs very sporadically on edaphically favoured sites (e.g. Kürschner and Neef, 2011). Acacia and tamarix were and are commonly used as firewood, until today tamarix species are used for buildings and acacia trees offer browsing even when other pastures fail (e.g. Baierle, 1993 : 116; Ghazanfar, 1998 : 260). The mentioned local elements are underrepresented in pollen spectra (e.g. Horowitz 1992 : 49), thus – despite their low frequencies – these taxa were present and available.

Local to regional elements :

Haloxylon/Aerva type includes species like *Haloxylon persicum* and *Haloxylon salicornicum*. Especially for adjacent regions in the north like the Iran and Jordan *Haloxylon persicum* is known and used as excellent firewood and (camel) pastures (e.g. Baierle, 1993 : 126 ff; Neef, 2011). Today, *Haloxylon salicornicum* is dominating in northern Arabia. Similar to *Haloxylon persicum* it is used as firewood

and pastures (e.g. Thalen, 1979 : 156). The continuously high frequencies of the *Haloxyton/Aerva* type in the Tayma pollen diagram indicate that at least until the mid-Holocene this firewood and pasture resource was abundant.

Capparidaceae, probably representing mainly *Capparis* type including caper (*Capparis spinosa*), is recorded throughout the sequence, with increasing frequencies in the uppermost section. An intentional human preservation thus seems probable. The same seems to hold true for *Dodonaea*. It is spread worldwide today, and the expansion of the sand olive (*Dodonaea angustifolia*) with its wide ecological range is favoured by humans (e.g. Umer *et al.*, 2007). It is appreciated because of its hard and heavy wood, its charcoal and for medical purposes as well (e.g. Dharani, 2002). The two taxa probably were present locally in the past, *Capparis* grows even today in the Tayma region on edaphically favoured sites.

The interpretation of the in the Tayma pollen diagram recorded olive (*Olea*) frequencies is ambiguous. The *Olea* pollen type includes wild species such as wild olives (*Olea europaea* subsp. *sylvestris* or subsp. *africana*) and the cultivated olive (*Olea europaea*). The *Olea* record starts during the early Holocene, and at about 7500 cal BP the frequencies increase. During this period arid conditions are assumed to prevail (ca. 8000–6300 cal BP, see above), a natural olive propagation triggered by increased precipitation thus seems improbable. On the other hand an olive cultivation starting as early as 7500 cal BP seems unlikely too : The southern Levant pollen records and archaeobotanical investigations congruently reveal the onset of olive cultivation around 6300/6500 cal BP (e.g. Litt *et al.*, 2012 ; Neumann *et al.*, 2007 and therein cited literature). Assuming an olive propagation triggered by climatic fluctuations, the Hijaz mountains and its foreland may be the natural habitats.

Regional elements :

Pistachio (*Pistacia*), oaks (*Quercus*) and hackberry (*Celtis*) are recorded regularly throughout the sequence with low frequencies. The slightly increased frequencies during probably wetter periods of pistachio and oak and the continuous record suggest an at least regional presence of the trees, most probably in the Hijaz mountains and its forelands about 100 km in the west of Tayma. Assuming a similar wind regime in the past (dominating NW winds, meteoblue) the mountainous vegetation in the west should be represented in the pollen record. The southernmost occurrence of oaks (*Quercus*) today is a population in the northernmost Midian mountains (Deil and al Gifri, 1998 : 129). A southward expansion of these steppic woodlands along the Midian/Hijaz mountains during the early and mid-Holocene seems probable. Pistachio even may have grown closer to Tayma : Today, pistachio trees can be found in the Negev and Edom mountains in Jordan, the Jebel Lawz in northwestern Saudi Arabia and the montane woodlands in southern Arabia at higher elevations (Deil and al Gifri, 1998 ; Kürschner, 1998). Considering that *Pistacia* is under-represented in pollen spectra (e.g. Bottema, 1986) and that even today pistachios penetrate far into arid regions alongside wadis or fissures, where precipitation alone is insufficient for their growth (e.g. Baierle, 1993 : 72-73), it seems possible that pistachios grew – perhaps intentionally promoted – on edaphically favoured habitats near Tayma.

Other pollen types (may) include further woody taxa. They are not mentioned here because these taxa could (at least at the current state of analysis) not further be specified.

Pastures (for wild animal populations and herded animal populations)

For a short, early Holocene period (ca. 8700–8000 cal BP) additional (favoured) pastures – grasses – expanded. Whether the slight increase of amongst other *Centaurea* and *Fagonia* frequencies in the upper most part may be interpreted as indicative for grazing has to be decided when the diagram is completed (cf Woldring, 2002 ; Baierle, 1993)

Summary and Conclusion

The ^{14}C -dated Tayma pollen record of northwestern Arabia – based on AMS dates of pollen concentrations – reveals the major significance of climate for the early and mid-Holocene vegetation fluctuations in this region :

Desert vegetation, represented by amongst other high Chenopodiaceae frequencies, prevailed during the Holocene at least on edaphically unfavoured sites. Yet, at least for hydrologically and edaphically favoured sites important vegetation shifts are documented :

- A brackish, shallow lake was built up about 9300 cal BP under prevailing arid conditions.
- Between about 8700-8000 cal BP *Ephedra* and mainly grasslands spread, indicating the wettest conditions during the Holocene.
- Around 8000 cal BP the grasslands retreated abruptly and more drought-resistant desert-shrublands and sage brush formations spread. Together with distinct diminished sedimentation rates arid conditions are assumed for the first part of the mid-Holocene (ca. 8000–6300 cal BP).
- A short period of slightly wetter conditions may be documented by increased sage brush and tree frequencies between about 6300–5900 cal BP.
- Stands of local vegetation, mainly depending on high groundwater like tamarisk, acacia and sumac, were not affected by the secular climate variations.
- Anthropogenic impact is recorded at least since about 6300 cal BP with the recorded crop cultivation. Whether the increase of olive frequencies around 7500 cal BP attests cultivation or not remains an open question.

In the Tayma pollen diagram of northwestern Arabia human impact is approved since 6300 cal BP. Yet, the documented vegetation dynamics during the early, mid and first part of the late Holocene (9300-4800 cal BP) are assumed to be related to climate change rather than connected to anthropogenic land use.

Especially the early Holocene vegetation shift evidencing wetter conditions induced changes in the natural biotic resources, supplying additional pastures. The presumably generally slightly wetter conditions during the existence of a palaeolake at Tayma and/or less intensive management of landscapes during this period provided (at least) woody resources in the region which are missing today.

Answering the initial question, whether human land use was relevant for shaping the natural vegetation during the 1st half of the Holocene in the Tayma region, northwestern Saudi Arabia, it may be stated that climate was of major significance and human impact probably of only local relevance.

Acknowledgements

Special thanks belong to the Fritz Thyssen Stiftung für Wissenschaftsförderung for funding, enabling the palynological investigations by MD and the DFG for supporting the completion of the palynological part as contribution of the CLEAR project (Holocene CLimatic Events of Northern ARabia). We thank the archaeological team of Tayma, especially A. Hausleiter, A. Intilia, S. Lora and M. Al-Najm, for their supply not only during field work. Special thanks belong to Viola Podsiadlowski and Livius Hauser for the assistance of sample preparation.

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